

Completely Secure Alternative Quantum Key Distribution with High Bit Rates Over Long Distances

Arindam Mitra

Independent researcher

GPO, Post Box: 50, Kolkata, West Bengal, India, 700001

Abstract:: At present, quantum key distribution (QKD) can generate completely secure keys over a small distance (~5 km) with a poor bit rate (~10 bits/s) using untrusted devices in practical settings. In addition, QKD requires the support of a classical authentication scheme to ensure security. Here, we present the idea of an alternative QKD that can generate completely secure keys over a large distance (~100 km) with an estimated high bit rate (~ 10^6 bits/s) using untrusted devices in practical settings. We also point out that entangled states can be used for quantum communication and that messages can be entangled.

Inspired by Wiesner's seminal work [1] on quantum cryptography, the idea of quantum key distribution (QKD) [2–4] was developed. QKD attracted widespread attention [5–10] because it promised complete/unconditional security based on the no-cloning principle [11,12].

After four decade of research it has been found [9,10] that QKD cannot deliver completely secure keys in practice when devices may be untrusted. Due to this development, it was thought that a stronger quantum principle than no-cloning principle is required to achieve the goal. This led to the idea of device-independent (DI) QKD [13,14], which can, in principle, provide complete security through the violation of a Bell inequality. Recently, some DI-QKD schemes have been experimentally implemented over short distances and with low bit rates [15–17]. This is encouraging as well as frustrating. Achieving Bell-inequality violation over long distances is extremely challenging, and QKD schemes such as BB-84 [2], which use unentangled states, cannot be used. Against this backdrop, several groups have demonstrated QKD over distances exceeding 100 km [18–24]. The development of secure quantum communication networks requires QKD to generate completely secure keys over long distances, even with untrusted devices.

Several questions naturally arise. Can the no-cloning principle ensure completely secure QKD with untrusted devices without requiring a violation of Bell's inequality ? Can quantum mechanics alone provide security for QKD without relying on a classical authentication scheme ? Are these practical and conceptual issues of QKD fundamentally correlated ?

To address these questions, we propose an alternative quantum encryption scheme in which two sequences of quantum states encode the bit values 0 and 1 and are described by the same density matrix, $\rho^0 = \rho^1$. In alternative QKD, instead of two sequences we shall use n sequences of quantum states all represented by the same density matrix, $\rho_1^1 = \rho_1^0 = \rho_2^1 = \rho_2^0 = \rho_3^1 = \rho_3^0 = \dots = \rho_n^0$ to encode two bit values. As noted by von Neumann [25], different mixtures represented by identical density matrices cannot be distinguished. This can be called as density-matrix indistinguishability (DMI) principle. Nevertheless, the receiver can distinguish between the two possible sequence ensembles represented by the same density matrix if the receiver knows sequence codes in advance. An eavesdropper cannot distinguish the randomly mixed n sequence-mixtures by any known [9,10] or unknown attacks, primarily due to the DMI principle [25]. Moreover, neither the DMI principle nor the no-cloning principle can be rendered ineffective, as the two principles are complimentary to each other. Alternative QKD can generate completely secure key over distances and bit rates with much much higher than the existing QKD.

To illustrate the idea of alternative QKD, we shall present a scheme employing unentangled states. Suppose Alice has a stock of horizontally polarized photons and an ideal coin. She can prepare superposition states using a symmetric (1:1) beam splitter leading to two paths "s" and "r". Alice prepares two superposition states as follows: She tosses the coin and, based on the outcome, performs the following operations: If the toss yields "tails" (T), she rotates the polarization by 90° in path "s". If the toss yields "heads" (H) she does nothing. In path "r", she does nothing regardless of the outcome. The states prepared in this way can be written as

$$|\Psi_1\rangle_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\leftrightarrow\rangle_r + |\leftrightarrow\rangle_s)$$

$$|\Psi_2\rangle_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\leftrightarrow\rangle_r + |\updownarrow\rangle_s)$$

Alice can prepare a sequence S_0 of the above states representing bit 0 by tossing coin N times. She can prepare another pair of superposition states as follows: She tosses the coin, and based on the outcome, performs the following operations. If the coin toss result is "heads" (H), she rotates the polarization by 45° in the path "s". If the coin toss result is "tails" (T), she rotates the polarization by 135° in path "s". In the other path "r", she does nothing. The states prepared in this way can be written as

$$|\phi_1\rangle_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\leftrightarrow\rangle_r + |\nearrow\rangle_s)$$

$$|\phi_2\rangle_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\leftrightarrow\rangle_r + |\nwarrow\rangle_s)$$

Alice can prepare a sequence S_1 of the above states, representing bit 1 by tossing coin N times. The states $|\Psi_1\rangle, |\Psi_2\rangle, |\phi_1\rangle, |\phi_2\rangle$ are mutually non-orthogonal to each other. The density matrices of these two sequences are the same in the basis $\{|\leftrightarrow\rangle_r, |\updownarrow\rangle_r, |\leftrightarrow\rangle_s, |\updownarrow\rangle_s\}$.

$$\rho^0 = \rho^1 = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Alice secretly share the preparation codes of S^0 and S^1 with Bob. Alice transmits either S^0 or S^1 to Bob. Now he has to decode the bit value. Suppose Bob sets an analyzer either at 0^0 or at 45^0 at the end of the path “s”. The projection operators corresponding to these two settings are denoted by P_1 and P_2 . If P_1 is applied to $|\Psi_2\rangle_i$ and P_2 is applied to $|\phi_2\rangle_i$, the measurement yields a positive result with probability $1/4$. However, if P_1 is applied to $|\phi_2\rangle_i$ and P_2 is applied to $|\Psi_2\rangle_i$, the measurement yields a null result with probability 1. Since Bob knows the sequence codes, he can identify the two sequences. A single positive result is enough to identify the sequence. For example, suppose P_1 gives a positive result. Bob correctly identifies the states as $|\phi_2\rangle_i$ and decodes the bit value as 1.

To ensure security Alice and Bob will secretly share a third sequence, S^A , of quantum states for quantum authentication. Eavesdropper, called Eve, could not recover bit value from the single copy of the sequence S^0 or S^1 , since $\rho^0 = \rho^1$ [25]. Any attempt to disturb a sequence or state will inevitably introduce errors with a nonzero probability. After recovering the bit value, if Bob does not detect any errors, he will send an authentication sequence S^A to Alice. If Alice also detects no errors in S^A , she will send the next sequence S^0 or S^1 . In this two-way communication, bit-by-bit security can be achieved through bit-by-bit quantum authentication. Instead of four different sequences of quantum states, two different sequences of the same two non-orthogonal states [26] representing the same density matrices can also be used to achieve bit-by-bit security.

It is believed [5] that entanglement by itself cannot be used for communication. Following alternative quantum coding, entanglement can be used [27] to communicate. In other words, message can be entangled. Two distinct arrangements of EPR [28] particles can represent bits 0 and 1. As for example,

$$S^1 = \{A, B, B, C, D, A, E, F, E, F, C, D, \dots\}$$

$$S^0 = \{B, A, D, C, D, A, E, E, F, F, B, C, \dots\}$$

Here the same pair of letters, ZZ, denotes an EPR pair, specifically a singlet state of spin 1/2 particles, which can be described as,

$$|\Psi\rangle_{i,j} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(|\uparrow\rangle_i |\downarrow\rangle_j - |\downarrow\rangle_i |\uparrow\rangle_j \right)$$

where i and j ($i \neq j$) denote the position of a pair in the sequence, and \uparrow and \downarrow denote two opposite spin directions. In the above example, the two sequences S^1 and S^0 are non-overlapping because positions of EPR pairs, $Z_i Z_j$, in S^1 and S^0 are different. The two sequences can be represented by the same density matrices: $\rho^0 = \rho^1$.

Alice and Bob share the sequence codes. Alice transmits either S^0 or S^1 to Bob. After receiving the sequence, Bob measures the spin components of all particles along z axis. EPR pair yields $\uparrow\downarrow$ or $\downarrow\uparrow$ results with equal probability. Non-EPR pair yields $\uparrow\downarrow$ or $\downarrow\uparrow$ or $\uparrow\uparrow$ or $\downarrow\downarrow$ results with equal probability. Bob can conclusively identify a non-EPR pair, if he gets $\uparrow\uparrow$ or $\downarrow\downarrow$ results. Suppose Bob sorts out a probable non-EPR pair from the incoming sequence assuming it to be S^0 . If the chosen pair does not yield any conclusive non-EPR data, he sorts out another probable non-EPR pair assuming it to be S^1 . Thus, he sorts out probable non-EPR pairs alternately assuming S^0 and S^1 and continues measurements until he gets conclusive non-EPR data. In this approach, Bob is alternately sorts out EPR and non-EPR pair since the two probable sequences are non-overlapping. Therefore, he can quickly recover the bit value. Alternatively, Bob can recover bit value by recovering 100% EPR correlation from the sequence of entangled states. Due to entanglement, quantum communication using entangled states is possible. In the same way, in quantum communication or alternative QKD with entangled states, bit-by-bit security with bit-by-bit quantum authentication can be achieved.

Let us discuss the security of our alternative QKD schemes under non-ideal conditions. Due to loss and noise, Eve can intercept some percentage of each transmitted sequence and try to correlate the results of measurements on different transmitted sequences of states to decode S^0 and S^1 . From a measurement on any state, Eve cannot conclusively identify the state, but she can gain information from the result. The number of successful measurement outcomes X and the amount of information gained from the measurements are not equivalent. However, for any measurement, the expected number of results, $\mathbb{E}[X]$, is directly proportional to the expected information gain when the information gain per successful outcome is constant. So results from multiple identical sequences S^0 or S^1 cannot be correlated, if $\mathbb{E}[X]$ from the measurements on N identical sequences S^0 or S^1 is close to 0. In other words, Eve's expected information gain of the generated key K_i will be $I_{\text{exp.}}(E:K_i) \approx 0$, if $\mathbb{E}[X] \approx 0$.

Eve's probability of obtaining a result A from a single quantum state $|\xi\rangle_i$ is p_a . Eve's probability of obtaining the results A from m states $|\xi\rangle_1, |\xi\rangle_2, |\xi\rangle_3, \dots, |\xi\rangle_m$ belonging to either S^0 and S^1 is, $P = (p_a)^m$. Her expected number of results A from independent measurements, which can be considered as binomial trail, on the N copies of sequence (S^0 or S^1) of the same m states is $\mathbb{E}[X] = P.N$. To lower $\mathbb{E}[X]$, number (N) of reuse can be restricted. But the scheme should produce secure bits more than the secure bits it used. Then only new pair of sequences can be prepared using the securely generated bits to rerun the protocol. For a 10-fold gain of secure bits, if we consider $N = 100000$, $p_a = 0.25$, $m = 10$, $L = 100$ km, then we obtain $\mathbb{E}[X] \gg 0$ and $I_{\text{exp.}}(E:K_i) \gg 0$. The scheme crashes for this usage. We have to find out a way, how two sequences can be restrictively reused so that $\mathbb{E}[X] \approx 0$ and $I_{\text{exp.}}(E:K_i) \approx 0$.

Complete Secure Alternative QKD with Untrusted Devices: Instead of single pair of sequences, two pairs of sequences S_1^1 and S_1^0 , and S_2^1 and S_2^0 can be used to simultaneously generate double bits to generate two keys K_1 and K_2 . Two sequences each taking from each pair can be embedded in random positions to generate double bits at a time. That is, S_1^1 or S_1^0 will be encoded in the random positions S_1^p ; and S_2^1 or S_2^0 will be encoded in random positions S_2^p . The two pairs of sequences of quantum states produce identical density matrices: $\rho_1^1 = \rho_1^0 = \rho_2^1 = \rho_2^0$. Therefore, the four transmitted sequences carrying double bits can be denoted as

$$S_{12}^{11} \equiv S_1^1 + S_2^1; S_{12}^{00} \equiv S_1^0 + S_2^0; S_{12}^{10} \equiv S_1^1 + S_2^0; S_{12}^{01} \equiv S_1^0 + S_2^1$$

Here, S_{12}^{10} carries 1 0 which will go to K_1 and K_2 respectively. The two pairs of sequences will be repeatedly used to generate K_1 and K_2 simultaneously. Similarly, n pairs of sequences can be used to generate n keys $\{K_1, K_2, K_3, \dots, K_n\}$ simultaneously. Each pair of sequences S_i^1 and S_i^0 occupies the same random positions S_n^p . Therefore, n pairs of sequences can be denoted as

$$S_{123\dots n}^{111\dots 1} \equiv S_1^1 + S_2^1 + S_3^1 \dots S_n^1; S_{123\dots n}^{000\dots 0} \equiv S_1^0 + S_2^0 + S_3^0 + \dots S_n^0.$$

$$S_{123\dots n}^{110\dots 1} \equiv S_1^1 + S_2^1 + S_3^0 + \dots S_n^1; S_{123\dots n}^{101\dots 0} \equiv S_1^1 + S_2^0 + S_3^1 + \dots S_n^0$$

$$S_{123\dots n}^{010\dots 1} \equiv S_1^0 + S_2^1 + S_3^0 + \dots S_n^1; S_{123\dots n}^{001\dots 0} \equiv S_1^0 + S_2^0 + S_3^1 + \dots S_n^0$$

Alice and Bob secretly share sequences codes of all the pairs as well as positional codes $S_1^p, S_2^p, S_3^p, \dots, S_n^p$. The n pairs of sequences of quantum states produce identical density matrices: $\rho_1^1 = \rho_1^0 = \rho_2^1 = \rho_2^0 = \rho_3^1 = \rho_3^0 = \dots = \rho_n^1 = \rho_n^0$. In this final scheme, all sequences contain the same set of randomly distributed non-orthogonal states or identical entangled states, ensuring that the devices respond identically for all sequences.

Let us discuss the security of this final scheme. Eve can attack the channel and intercept some percentage of each transmitted sequence $S_{123\dots n}^{***\dots*}$ and try to gain information about a sequence S_i^1 or S_i^0 by correlating the results of her measurements. For this, she has to target at least some states $|\xi\rangle_{ij}, |\xi\rangle_{ik}, |\xi\rangle_{il}, \dots, |\xi\rangle_{iz}$ of S_i^1 or S_i^0 , occupying j -th, k -th, l -th, \dots , z -th positions of $S_{123\dots n}^{***\dots*}$ respectively. As sequences S_i^1 and S_i^0 are randomly reused, Eve's expected information gain about a sequence S_i^1 or S_i^0 will not be possible only if the expected score of her measurements on the same states $|\xi\rangle_{ij}, |\xi\rangle_{ik}, |\xi\rangle_{il}, \dots, |\xi\rangle_{iz}$ is almost zero.

Eve's probability of obtaining a result A from a single quantum state $|\xi\rangle_{ij}$ is p_a . The positional probability of the states $|\xi\rangle_{ij}$ is, $p_n = \frac{1}{2^n}$. Eve's probability of obtaining the results A from m states $|\xi\rangle_{ij}, |\xi\rangle_{ik}, |\xi\rangle_{il}, \dots, |\xi\rangle_{iz}$ is, $P = (p_n \cdot p_a)^m$. Her expected number of scores (result A) of measurements on the same m states $|\xi\rangle_{ij}, |\xi\rangle_{ik}, |\xi\rangle_{il}, \dots, |\xi\rangle_{iz}$ for N reuses of S_i^1 and S_i^0 is $\mathbb{E}[X] = P \cdot N$. If $p_n \approx 0$, then by choosing a small N , it is possible to make $\mathbb{E}[X] \approx 0$.

Eve can try to exploit noise and imperfect devices—detectors, sources, channels, random number generators, electronics, etc. [9,10]. An imperfect source can emit multi-photon pulses. If an imperfect source emits multi-photon pulses 100% of the time, users would have to abort all QKD protocols.

Therefore, Alice and Bob must allow multi-photon emission with a maximum probability p_0 . Eve can manipulate the source to set the probability of multi-photon emission p_x , but it must be less than or equal to p_0 . Alice can verify this.

Due to noise and loss, Eve can intercept some percentage of each sequence to gain information about S_i^1 or S_i^0 from multi-photon pulses. Let us assume that an unknown multi-photon quantum state can be known after measurement with probability 1. Thus, multi-photon states can be correlated to gain information about bit values. To foil this attack, Alice will select multi-photon states at some positions in each sequence as decoy states ρ^0 and ρ^1 , at random, with probability p_0 . That is, Alice injects decoy state ρ^0 and ρ^1 at random in each bit-carrying state ρ_i^1 with probability p_0 . Similarly, she injects decoy state ρ^0 and ρ^1 at random in each bit-carrying state ρ_i^0 with probability p_0 . Although multi-photon states can be identified by Eve, they remain uncorrelated and do not reveal any bit value.

Exploiting source eavesdropper can produce equivalent sequence-ensembles of states $\{ \rho_1^1 = \rho_1^0 = \rho_2^1 = \rho_2^0 = \rho_3^1 = \rho_3^0 = \dots \dots \rho_n^1 = \rho_n^0 \}$, instead of the specified equivalent sequence-ensembles $\{ \rho_1^1 = \rho_1^0 = \rho_2^1 = \rho_2^0 = \rho_3^1 = \rho_3^0 = \dots \dots = \rho_n^1 = \rho_n^0 \}$, but she cannot produce non-equivalent sequence-ensembles $\rho_i^1 \neq \rho_i^0$. Be that as it may, it is practically impossible for Eve to distinguish any of her equivalent sequence-ensembles $\{ \rho_1^1 = \rho_1^0 = \rho_2^1 = \rho_2^0 = \rho_3^1 = \rho_3^0 = \dots \dots \rho_n^1 = \rho_n^0 \}$, if $\mathbb{E}[X] \approx 0$.

Like imperfect sources, imperfect detectors, electronics, RNGs, and channels, etc., these will behave identically for all pairs of sequences—all of which contain the same set of quantum states. The bit value is not encoded in the quantum states but in the sequence of states. Users can memorize the sequence - codes or keep in hard copy. That is why device imperfections do not matter. Only the statistics of reuse of sequences matter. Thus, untrusted devices cannot reveal any information about any sequence. For all known [9,10] and unknown eavesdropping attacks, $I_{\text{exp.}}(E:K_i) \approx 0$, if $\mathbb{E}[X] \approx 0$.

Transmission over 10 km and 100 km of optical fiber will yield $\mathbb{E}[X] \approx 0$ for the chosen values of $N = 100000$, $p_a = 0.25$, $m=10$, $n= 1000$, which are given in the table below. To increase $\mathbb{E}[X]$, Eve can choose m less than 10. However, a small m means the statistical confidence of her identification will be lower and $\mathbb{E}[X]$ will still remain much much less than 1. According to the need, the transmission distance, the number of reuses and the bit rate can be chosen as long as $\mathbb{E}[X] \approx 0$ and the receiver can reliably recover the bit values. Consequently, no error correction or privacy amplification, no violation of the Bell inequality is required. Even bit-by-bit security checking is not required. Like the one-time-pad system [28], the eavesdropper has no option other than guessing. Due to statistical constraints on code reuse, it is impossible for the eavesdropper to render the DMI principle, as well as the no-cloning principle, ineffective.

As complete security can be achieved with zero failure probability over long distances, it is feasible to build a secure quantum communication network using sequences of single-photon states. In the final scheme sequences of entangled states can be used, but it needs multiple delay lines since storing entangled states for long times in quantum memory is yet to be practically achieved. Completely secure quantum communication with entangled states is also possible over a long distance.

It has been reported [29,30] that over 100 km of optical fiber, the highest raw key generation rate of about 10^7 bits/s has been achieved using 10 GHz pulses [15–24]. The corresponding secure bit rate is further reduced after post-processing. As post-processing is not required in the present scheme, the

reported raw bit rates of QKD schemes [29,30] can be used as a reference for estimating the secure bit rate of this scheme. In the present scheme, only 15–30 surviving states from each sequence are sufficient to recover the bit values with a high success probability. Thus, the detection of 15–30 raw bits in QKD is approximately equivalent to the detection of one completely secure bit in the present scheme. Consequently, over 100 km and 200 km of optical fiber, the estimated total bit rates of the present scheme are $\sim 10^6$ bits/s and $\sim 10^5$ bits/s, respectively, where the total bit rate = (bit rate per key) \times N.

Entanglement offers new possibilities in quantum communication. Due to entanglement, each bit of information can be fragmented [31,32]. A single bit of information can be uniquely split and distributed across multiple locations. For example, bit 1 can be split into two entangled sequences where EPR particles and their partners are arranged in the two entangled sequences in direct order, and bit 0 can be split into another pair of entangled sequences where EPR particles and their partners are arranged in the two entangled sequences in reverse order. This encoding facilitates two-step communication, which can be used in bit commitment [32], and each bit of information can be distributed in two locations.

One of the important goals of human civilization is the search for extraterrestrial signals [33]. One intriguing possibility is that an alien civilization might use sequences of entangled states to encode binary information, enabling us to recover bit values without requiring prior knowledge of the specific sequence codes. They may even choose to communicate by splitting each bit of information into multiple entangled parts using multi-particle entangled states. Likewise, we could use similar techniques to communicate with them. Entanglement could provide a potential framework for both secure and insecure forms of quantum communication with extraterrestrial life, if they exist.

The power of alternative quantum coding warrants further exploration to fully assess its potential in quantum information. A comparison between standard and alternative quantum coding may also provide insights into the longstanding foundational debate [34] on individual versus statistical quantum state descriptions. It has been reported that unconditionally secure quantum bit commitment [35,36] and quantum coin tossing are impossible [37]. These reports are based on standard coding. We have revisited [32,38] the reports following using an entanglement-based alternative quantum coding. Different possibilities of entanglement in communication and the preservation of information are yet to be explored.

In conclusion, it would be always advantageous and fundamentally important if a scientific problem can be solved classically as well as quantum mechanically. There is a possibility that like QKD, classical key distribution (CKD) can be completely secure. We have explored the possibility [39].

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Table

Length of optical fiber in Km: L	Loss of states	No. of states in $S_i^{0/1}$	No. of pairs of sequences: n	Prob. of each key: p_n	Eve's prob. of getting result A: p_a	No. of reuse of $S_i^{0/1}$: N	Gain after N reuse: G	Eve's no. of measured states per seq. : M	Eve's expected score : $\mathbb{E}[X]$	Estimated total bits/s using 10-GHz pulse
10	~40%	10^3	10^3	10^{-3}	0.25	10^4	10	10	$\sim 10^{-26}$	$\sim 10^7$
100	~99%	10^4	10^3	10^{-3}	0.25	10^5	10	10	$\sim 10^{-25}$	$\sim 10^6$

$$\text{Gain of secure bits, } G = \frac{\text{No. of used bits per sequence}}{\text{No. of generated bits after N reuse of each sequence}}$$